

Applying Image Segmentation to 19th Century Cartographic Data for Categorical Woodland Mapping in Wales

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Abstract

Identifying historic woodland is useful for future planning, to help target areas where woodland previously existed, and therefore is well suited to support tree growth. This study applies a fine-tuned masked regional convolutional neural network model to predict areas of woodland on 19th Century maps in Wales. Each area of woodland is assigned a specific woodland category, and geospatial processing techniques are applied to produce a dataset, which is publicly available, that indicates where different types of woodland existed.

Our research shows the model performs better at predicting areas of woodland with distinct woodland types, such as Broadleaf and Conifer. However, we highlight the importance of accurately labelling ground truth objects, and the difficulty in segmenting woodland areas with less detailed map symbols. We conclude although this dataset can be used to provide new insights to support woodland creation schemes, it is not suitable for statistical analysis without further refinement.

Keywords: historic mapping, image segmentation, geospatial analysis

1. Introduction

There are numerous areas where woodland clearance has taken place, especially during the 19th century. (Peterken 2002) These areas of historic woodland may be better suited for replanting and woodland creation schemes, if the original soil contains a remnant seed store or an established root network (Forestry Commission 2024).

However, current historic woodland data sources in Wales only capture areas of historic woodland that still exist today¹. Manually labelling the remaining areas is a time intensive process, requires expert domain knowledge, and can result in inconsistencies across large areas.

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¹ [Natural Resources Wales / Identifying ancient woodlands](#)

In this study, we present an alternative approach, that combines computer vision modelling alongside geospatial processing techniques, to create a dataset of predicted historic woodland (categorised by tree type) in Wales.

2. Data Preparation

2.1. Data Source

Ordnance Survey (OS) began comprehensive mapping (25-inch to the mile) of Wales in the 19th century. Each of Wales's 13 historic counties were mapped over a period of 50 years (1843-1893), with some upland areas excluded. After analysis, we estimate the coverage of the OS Historic Mapping Series is approximately 90% of the total area of Wales², with “missing” areas concentrated to areas in Brecknockshire (Brecon) and Caernarvonshire (Caernarfon).

We chose the higher resolution 25 inch to the mile maps for this work, due to the level of detail captured for the mapped features. Different types of woodland are depicted by distinct tree symbols, as shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. Derived from OS County Series Mapping (Landmark, 1:2500) – Anglesey, Wales (1889)

Using the supporting historic map documentation archived by the National Library of Scotland³, and in consultation with Cadw, Wales's historic environment service, we identified seven different woodland categories.

² Based on both modern and historic boundaries, so this figure is an estimate only

³ [Ordnance Survey Characteristic Sheets - Map Images - National Library of Scotland](#)

Figure 2. Example symbols representing each woodland category, derived from OS County Series Mapping (Landmark, 1:2500, 1843-1893)

Early testing of the model showed some shoreline and non-woodland features, such as sheepfolds and railway tracks, were incorrectly predicted as woodland, as seen in previous studies (Kramer & Painter. 2023). To address this, we also included two exclusion categories, “Shoreline” and “Cliff-like structures”. During post-processing, we removed predictions in these categories, to leave only actual woodland areas in the dataset, reducing the chance of coastal and anthropogenic features being mis-predicted as a woodland category.

2.2. Creating labelled dataset

Previous research has demonstrated that image segmentation models can be successfully applied to predict general woodland areas on lower resolution historic maps in England (Kramer & Painter 2023).

Based on this approach, we split each historic map into multiple images using a grid, so each individual image covered an area of 4ha (200m by 200m). In total, we created 593,555 images from the historic OS County Series Maps for Wales and saved them as non-georeferenced raster files.

From this image set, 2,195 (0.37%) were selected through stratified sampling for manual labelling, using features such as location, distance to coast and an area’s rural/urban classification⁴. This approach ensured a representative sample of images of different landscapes were used for training and model evaluation.

To ensure consistency between labellers, an area was only labelled as woodland if it contained three or more neighbouring tree stamps. The set of labelled images were split into a sample for training (65%), testing (20%) and validation (15%).

⁴ [Rural/urban classifications - Office for National Statistics](#)

3. Predictive Modelling

Many studies have shown how convolutional neural networks (CNN) can be used to accurately predict different features on historic maps, such as using U-Net CNNs to segment wetland (O'Hara *et al.* 2024) and built-up areas (Litvine *et al.* 2024) within historic Ordnance Survey maps.

In this work, we fine-tuned a Mask R-CNN deep learning model (He *et al.* 2017), with a ResNet-50 backbone for feature extraction, using the training and testing samples of manually labelled images. This model returns a bounding box, precise location, label and confidence score for each prediction, as shown in *Figure 3*.

Figure 3. Predicted Bush area in Monmouthshire, Wales, 1889, map derived from OS County Series (Landmark, 1:2500)

We used average precision to measure the model's performance during training. This metric is calculated by taking the average area under the precision-recall curves at different intersection under union (IoU) thresholds.⁵ The best performing model returned a mean average precision (across all woodland and exclusion categories) of 0.5.

The results showed that woodland categories with defined, distinctive, stamping, such as Broadleaf and Conifer, were the best performing. These categories also had a higher number of labelled objects in the training data compared to other woodland types, such as Orchard, that are less prevalent across Wales. (Oram *et al.* 2014)

Orchard woodland returned the lowest average precision score of 0.32 and made up only 4% of all manually labelled woodland areas (compared to Broadleaf; 31% of manually labelled woodland areas).

⁵ IoU is a measure of the amount of overlap between a ground truth and predicted shape, to determine whether a prediction is considered "correct"

Category	Average Precision
Broadleaf	0.61
Brushwood	0.36
Bush	0.37
Conifer	0.73
Mixed Wood	0.56
Orchard	0.32
Osiers	0.53
Cliff-like structures	0.45
Shoreline	0.53

Table 1. Average Precision scores of each 9 labelled categories using a labelled test set of images (N=439)

4. Post Processing

We applied the fine-tuned model to the remaining images created from the OS Historic Mapping Series for Wales. The predictions from each image were georeferenced⁶ and combined to create a single geospatial dataset of historic woodland areas in Wales.

4.1. Shifted image creation

Initial quality assurance of the dataset highlighted an issue in larger areas of woodland, split across multiple images. Combining individual predictions from these images exposed visible grid boundaries, possibly where tree symbols (and resulting predictions) on the edges of an image had been truncated.

Figure 4. Predictions in Carmarthenshire, 1888, map derived from OS County Series (Landmark, 1:2500)

⁶ Converted to coordinate reference system ESPG:27700

To resolve this, we created a second set of images with a shifted grid. In these new images, the upper left corner of the original image became the centre of the shifted image and improved the quality and removed gaps between predictions in these areas.

Figure 5. Illustration of a “shifted image” - hashed line - compared to the “original image” - solid line

4.2. Removing overlapping areas

As well as introducing duplicate predictions from shifted images, we set the parameters of the base image segmentation model so allow multiple overlapping predictions in an image. This was to prioritise recall and minimise the risk of woodland areas being missed.

We applied a series of post processing techniques to combine these overlapping areas, decide a dominant woodland category and create a simplified, useable dataset of distinct areas of woodland:

- Created a buffer, to combine neighbouring (but non-touching) polygons into continuous areas of woodland
- Dissolved overlapping predictions of the same woodland category
- Where predictions of different woodland categories overlapped, clipped polygons with lower confidence score by those with higher confidence score
- Simplified boundaries and removed any woodland areas <0.5ha⁷

For each new processed polygon, we calculated a weighted confidence score (mean). The weights were assigned based on the area of each raw model prediction that made up the larger dissolved polygon (after processing).

In some cases, the boundaries of the post processed model predictions did not align the actual boundaries of woodland as depicted on the map, introducing artificial edges between woodland. This was a consequence of combining larger areas of different woodland categories, across multiple images, with similar confidence scores.

⁷ [Definition of trees and woodland - GOV.UK](https://www.gov.uk/guidance/definition-of-trees-and-woodland)

Figure 6. Various areas of Wales showing the impact of processing on model predictions, maps derived from OS County Series (Landmark, 1:2500, 1843-1893)

These post processing steps reduced the number of predicted woodland areas by 81%. However, the total area of woodland in the final processed dataset only decreased by 0.6% compared to the unique area covered by the raw model predictions.

This shows the post processing techniques addressed the issue of duplicate, overlapping areas within the raw model predictions. The number of predicted areas of woodland in the post processed dataset reduced, without significantly decreasing the overall area of woodland predicted (other than areas <0.5ha).

5. Conclusion

In this study, we demonstrate that computer vision models can be fine-tuned with data from high resolution historic maps to predict different categories of woodland in Wales. The final dataset provides new insights to where historic woodland may have existed in the past in Wales, which can be used to help identify areas of woodland clearance or growth.

However, improvements could be made to this approach, as highlighted by the drop in model performance for certain woodland categories. Taking into account these limitations, the current dataset is unsuitable for certain tasks, such as statistical calculations.

5.1. Future improvements

The difference in model performance across certain woodland categories could be a result of an imbalanced dataset for training and validation. To improve the sampling of the training data, other data sources could be used to identify and target specific woodland categories to label across Wales, such as traditional orchards⁸.

Another reason for the lower performance in Bush, Orchard and Brushwood categories could be the lack of detail in the symbols marking these types of trees. Whereas Broadleaf, Mixed Wood and Conifer stamps include specific features such as the trunk and branches on each tree, the symbols for the weakest performing categories are simpler and less distinctive to each other, as shown in *Figure 2*. Using a deeper backbone with more layers (for example a

⁸ [Traditional Orchards | DataMapWales](#)

ResNet-101 feature pyramid network) to improve feature extraction (He, K *et al.* 2016), may also improve predictions across these classes.

5.2 Potential use cases

Considering these limitations, we suggest these results are used alongside other data sources to indicate the likelihood of where different types of historic woodland existed in Wales. This can help build confidence among woodland creation proposers and support government targets, such as the National Forest for Wales⁹.

We have made the outputs available for download under the Open Government Licence for Public Sector Information on DataMapWales¹⁰, with clear guidance to help users understand what they are suitable for.

As this dataset was generated using a predictive model, and contains some uncertainty, we recommend these outputs are not used for calculating area coverage. Future work could look at addressing issues such as the drop in model performance for certain categories, incomplete coverage of the original historic maps and impact of post processing on the final predictions. However, for these reasons, using this dataset for statistical purposes is not appropriate.

With further refinement, this approach could feed into other strands of work, for example, applying the same method to historic maps in other countries, or later versions of these maps, enabling historic woodland coverage to be tracked over time.

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⁹ [National Forest for Wales | GOV.WALES](#)

¹⁰ DataMapWales is an open-source data platform for sharing public sector geospatial data and services in Wales

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